

NEW DIRECTIONS IN MODERN LITERATURE AND THE IMPORTANCE OF ARTISTIC TRANSLATION

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola zamonaviy adabiyotda yangi yoʻnalishlarning shakllanishi, badiiy tarjimaning ahamiyati va uning adabiy jarayondagi oʻrni haqida soʻz yuritadi. Yangi adabiy yoʻnalishlar va avangard uslublar, globalizatsiya, madaniy almashinuv va texnologik taraqqiyot taʼsirida yuzaga kelgan. Badiiy tarjima nafaqat milliy adabiyotlarning oʻzaro bogʻlanishini taʼminlab, balki yangi gʻoyalar, estetik qadriyatlar va madaniyatlarni tanishtirishda ham muhim rol oʻynaydi. Maqolada zamonaviy badiiy tarjimaning oʻziga xos jihatlari, tarjimonning roli va uning adabiyotga qoʻshgan hissasi tahlil etiladi.

Annotation: This article discusses the formation of new trends in modern literature, the importance of literary translation and its role in the literary process. New literary trends and avant-garde styles have emerged under the influence of globalization, cultural exchange and technological progress. Literary translation plays an important role not only in ensuring the interconnection of national literatures, but also in introducing new ideas, aesthetic values and cultures. The article analyzes the specific aspects of modern literary translation, the role of the translator and his contribution to literature.

Kalit soʻzlar: *Zamonaviy adabiyot, madaniy almashinuv, globalizatsiya, tarjimonning roli, adabiy tahlil, estetik qadriyatlar, adabiy jarayon, tarjimaning ahamiyati.*

Key words: *Modern literature, cultural exchange, globalization, the role of the translator, literary analysis, aesthetic values, literary process, the importance of translation.*

Introduction: Along with the development of modern literature, new literary trends and styles have emerged. Literary translation plays an important role in this process. Through translation, the literary heritage of one country comes to life in other languages and cultures, and also gives rise to new literary trends. New trends open the way to discovering new forms and themes of modern literature. Through translation, cultural ties between literatures are strengthened and interlingual dialogue grows. This article analyzes the characteristics of new trends in modern literature, the role of literary translation and its importance.

Modern literature is enriched with new trends and forms in the process of its dynamic development. In each new era, innovations appear in literature in response to social, cultural and scientific changes. Today, postmodernism, socialism, psychological realism and other modern literary trends are adding new dimensions to literary processes. Each of

these trends expresses its own worldview, individualism and social changes. These new forms and themes of modern literature undoubtedly increase the importance of literary translation in establishing contacts with other languages and cultures.

Literary translation plays an important role in the international dissemination of literature. Translations create connections not only between transformed forms of language, but also between cultural and aesthetic values. The skill of the translator, how he correctly reflects the work in reality, how he conveys it to a new audience, significantly affects the literary process. Through literary translation, cultural ties between literatures are strengthened, new trends and styles come closer to each other, and at the same time, contribute to the global development of modern literature.

This article analyzes the new trends occurring in modern literature, their characteristics, as well as the role and significance of literary translation in literature. We will consider how literary translation, as not only the translation of literature, but also a form of intercultural communication, affects the formation of modern literature.

Main part: Modern literature is undergoing various innovations and changes. New trends usually lead to the emergence of new ideas, forms and literary techniques. They mainly include new themes related to individualism, globalization, technological innovations and social changes. At the same time, trends such as postmodernism, fantasy, socialism and ecological literature have also found their place. Modern literature pays great attention to the inner world of the hero, internal conflicts and psychological analysis.

Literary translation is the process of transforming literary works from one language to another. This is not only a change in language, but also the creation of a new culture and literary tradition through the content, style and art of the work. The translator plays an important role in bringing his work to a new audience. In modern translation studies, translation is considered a means of establishing dialogue not only in language, but also in cultures. Through the high skill of translators, works written in other languages are revived in their own language and come to life.

A number of new methods and techniques have been developed in modern translation studies. For example, through the method of “approximation” (expressive translation), the translator seeks to accurately and completely reflect the content of the original work. Nowadays, with the spread of digital technologies and the Internet, automatic translation tools have also developed. However, for works of art, human translation is still considered the most effective, because it fully expresses the aesthetic and emotional aspects of the original work.

In modern literature, new trends are emerging in connection with various social, cultural and scientific changes. In today's literature, postmodernism, ecofiction, psychological realism, feminist literature, socialism and other new trends are increasingly widespread. Postmodernism, for example, abandons traditional literary forms and pays attention to fragmentation, intertextuality, irony. In works written in this direction, events are expressed in a complex, unexpected and multifaceted way. Ecofiction and ecological

literature, on the other hand, raise issues such as the relationship between nature and man, the plundering of natural resources.

In addition, psychological realism pays great attention to the inner world, emotions and processes of consciousness of a person. In feminist literature, the role of women in society and their struggle against injustice are being studied more. The development of new trends contributes to the wide distribution of literature and the expression of unique social views. Literary translation is a key tool in strengthening the connection of literature with other cultures and in the spread of new trends and forms. A translator is not only a language changer, but also a person who conveys the idea, aesthetic value and cultural elements expressed in the original work to another audience. Through translation, the literary heritage of one people is reflected in other languages, and at the same time, contacts with other cultures develop.

The importance of translation in modern literature plays a major role not only in strengthening intercultural ties, but also in ensuring the interaction of new literary trends. For example, modern trends such as postmodernism or ecofiction spread internationally through translation. Translation is also an important tool in introducing new literary forms and styles into other languages.

Modern translation methods are also changing. In addition to traditional "word-for-word" translation, more "creative" or "free" translation methods are now being used. In these methods, the translator seeks to reflect not only the meaning and idea of the original work, but also its aesthetic and emotional charge. In addition, the development of digital technologies and automatic translation tools has accelerated the translation process, but for works of art, a human translator is still essential.

In translation, it is necessary to take into account factors such as inter-linguistic differences, inter-cultural differences, and the specific style of the works. Each translation is unique in its own way, but it remains the main tool for achieving the goal - namely, to convey the content and aesthetics of the original work to another audience.

Result and discussions: New trends in modern literature and literary translation are changing and developing each other. New trends are introducing new ideas, themes and forms into literature. The translation process is the main tool for spreading these innovations around the world. Through literary translation, works written in other languages enter a new culture, enrich literary traditions and contribute to the global development of modern literature.

New trends in modern literature, with their aesthetic and ideological characteristics, are taking literary processes to a new level. Each of these trends is unique in fulfilling its goals and tasks, but they are spread globally with the help of literary translation. Translation is an important tool for expanding new forms and themes in modern literature on an international level and establishing cultural ties.

Modern translation methods and techniques give translators great freedom in adapting the original work to another language and culture. However, in the translation

process, it is necessary to take into account cultural, linguistic and aesthetic differences. The main goal of translation is not only to change the language, but also to fully and accurately express the work itself. At the same time, translation plays an important role in helping to spread new trends in modern literature and ensuring the survival of the literary heritage on a global scale.

As we have analyzed the relationship between new trends in modern literature and literary translation, literary translation should be considered not only as a process of transferring from one language to another, but also as a means of conveying one culture to another. The development of new trends and the role of translation in this process contribute to the fact that modern literature is becoming more global and diverse.

Conclusion: New trends and literary translation play a significant role in modern literature. Through translation, cultural ties between literatures are further strengthened, new literary forms and techniques are emerging. Translation is not only a process of changing the language, but also a process of conveying one culture to another. The development of new literary trends and literary translation helps to discover new forms and themes of modern literature.

New trends and the role of literary translation in modern literature are of incomparable importance. New trends, including postmodernism, ecological literature, feminist and psychological realism, bring new perspectives, ideas and styles to literature, further enriching the literary process. These trends not only enhance the uniqueness of literature, but also reflect social and cultural changes and help spread new ideas on a global scale.

Literary translation is an important tool in this process, developing the interaction of literary works with other languages and cultures. Through translation, the literary heritage of one people spreads around the world, and new works are enriched by other cultures, creating opportunities for mutual dialogue. The main thing in translation is to accurately and accurately express the meaning, aesthetic and cultural significance of the original work. Also, modern translation methods and techniques give translators more freedom in the creative process, which allows for an increase in the quality of translation and the spread of new trends around the world. At the same time, taking into account intercultural differences, the translation process has a significant impact on the global development of literature. In short, in modern literature, new trends and literary translation complement each other and contribute to the global development of literature. It is possible to expand and disseminate new forms and themes through translation, strengthen cultural dialogue, and discover new, diverse forms of literature.

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